

JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

ISSN 2467-9364
9 772467 936000 Print

YEAR 3

May 2017

VOLUME I

ISSUE 4

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual
Dependent variable: Average Score

Scatterplot
Dependent Variable: Average Score

COUNCIL FOR MATHEMATICS EDUCATION
KATHMANDU, NEPAL

Journal of Mathematics Education

Advisors

Prof. Dr. Madan Man Shrestha
 Prof. Dr. Ram Man Shrestha
 Prof. Dr. Bhadra Man Tuladhar
 Prof. Dr. Siddhi Prasad Koirala
 Prof. Dr. Hira Bahadur Maharjan
 Prof. Dinesh Raj Panta

Editorial Board

Prof. Dr. Hari Prasad Upadhyay
 Prof. Dr. Lekh Nath Sharma
 Prof. Uma Nath Pandey
 Prof. Maheshwor Prasad Upadhyay
 Dr. Ajay Singh
 Mr. J. B. Pradhan

Executive Editorial Board

Chief Executive Editor :
 Dr. Bishnu Khanal
Executive Editor :
 Dr. Ruma Manandhar

Copyright © 2015 by Council for Mathematics Education. All rights reserved. No part of this Journal may be used or reproduced in any manner whatsoever without written permission from the publisher except in the case of brief quotations embodied in articles and reviews.

* The views expressed in this Journal are the authors own and are not necessarily the ones endorsed by the Journal of Mathematics Education, except where it is obvious from the context that information published have been endorsed by the Journal of Mathematics Education.

NATIONAL EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE 2072

- | | |
|------------------------------------|---|
| 1. President: | Prof. Madan Man Shrestha, Ph.D.
9841295316 |
| 2. Senior Vice President: | Mr. Krishna Prasad Pohkrel
9841519746 |
| 3. Vice President (Prov.3): | Mr. Krishna Prasad Aryal
9855054236 |
| 4. Vice President (Prov.4): | Mr. Chintamani Sharma
9846033620 |
| 5. Vice President (Prov.5): | Mr. Lok Bahadur Basnet
9857831974 |
| 6. Vice President (Prov.7): | Mr. Raghubir Bhatta
9848422828 |
| 7. General Secretary: | Mr. Ramesh Prasad Awsthi
9841509174 |
| 8. Secretary (Acad.): | Mr. Shree Prasad Ghimiri
9841242562 |
| 9. Secretary (Admin.): | Mr. Bishnu Prasad Paneru
9841540289 |
| 10. Treasurer: | Mrs. Rachan Joshi
9841328532 |
| 11. Member (National): | Mr. Krishna Chandra Paudel
9841304549 |
| 12. Member (National): | Dr. Bishnu Khanal
9851060124 |
| 13. Member (National): | Dr. Ruma Manandhar
9849299654 |
| 14. Member (National): | Mr. Bhoj Raj Koirala 9846126641 |
| 15. Member (National): | Prof. Prakash M. Bajracharya, Ph.D.
9841719383 |
| 16. Member (National): | Mr. Krishna Bhakta Tuladhar
9851086844 |
| 17. Member (National): | Dr. Ajay Singh, 9843333739 |
| 18. Member (Prov.4): | Mr. Gyanendra Neupane, 9846416053 |
| 19. Member (Prov.1): | Mr. Jeevan Nepal, 9842931395 |
| 20. Member (Prov.2): | Mr. Raj Kumar Thapa, 9841580709 |

Publisher

Council for Mathematics Education
 Lalitpur, Kathmandu, Nepal
 G.P.O. Box: 12823
 E-mail : mathcouncil@gmail.com
 mathcouncilarticle@gmail.com
 Website : www.mathcouncilnepal.org.np

Marketing Department

Director : Mr. Krishna Chandra Paudel
 Dr. Bed Raj Acharya
 Mrs. Sarala Luitel

Price : Rs. 100/-

Office Address :

Lalitpur Secondary Boarding School
 Lagankhel, Lalitpur, Nepal
 Ph. No. 5522704

Layout Design :

Anil Kumar
 Prakash Wagle

Printed at :

Bara Offset Press
 Basundhara, Kathmandu
 Ph.: 01-4385825
 Mob. 9841189625
 E-mail: baraoffset@gmail.com

Journal of Mathematics Education

Year 3

May 2017

Volume I

Issue 4

Contents

	Topic	Author	Page
i.	Editorial		
1.	Teacher's Personalities and Mathematics Achievement: An Assessment	Dr. Baua Lal Sah	1
2.	Absolutist and Fallibilist View on the Nature of Mathematics	Dr. Bed Raj Acharya	9
3.	A Comparative Study on Learning Strategies of High and Low Performing Students on Mathematics	Ram Chandra Ghimire	13
4.	Remediation of Students' Mathematical Errors	Dr. Mukunda Prakash Kshetree	21
5.	Mathematics Educators' Teaching Styles in Constituent and Affiliated Campuses of Tribhuvan University	Dr. Bishnu Khanal	27
6.	Cultural Metaphors in Mathematics Teaching: A Constructivist Approach	Jaya Bishnu Pradhan	33
7.	Critical Thinking Strategies in Mathematics Classrooms	Narhari Acharya	43
8.	Students' Attitude towards Collaborative Instruction: A Constructivist Pedagogy	Navin Paudal	50
9.	Status on Availability and Use of ICT in Teaching Learning Activities in Higher Education	Shree Prasad Ghimire	56

Students' Attitude towards Collaborative Instruction: A Constructivist Pedagogy

Navin Paudal*

Background

In the context of Nepal, mathematics is regarded as a difficult subject by most of the students. Many students consider mathematics to be learned as rote memorization like remembering the tables, orders and formulae. This happens basically due to the process of learning mathematics in their early age using one way lecture method in which the students are forced to identify, remember and repeat after their teacher. Many teachers have also been discovered to have insufficient skills to present mathematical skills to the learners effectively. Teachers are using traditional drilling and reciting approach. In this context teaching mathematics is quite a challenging job.

Constructivist philosophy has a long history of application in education. It gives valuable insights to teachers to formulate the pedagogic strategies. After went through different articles related to constructivism, the researcher is motivated to change his teaching philosophy. So, the researcher begun to formulate different teaching strategies based on constructivist philosophy. Researcher used collaborative learning as one of such teaching strategy. This article is all about a teacher's try on the pedagogic approach used in his class based on constructivists' philosophy. Specially, this study is targeted to investigate the attitude of the students towards collaborative instruction.

The population of the researches comprises

all the students of class VII and IX of a school of Kathmandu valley. This school was chosen because of the researcher's own quest for knowing the attitude of his students towards collaborative learning in his class. Also, research at own working environment facilitates the researcher to obtain data easily. The Class VII consist of one hundred and twenty-nine (129) students and class IX consist of one hundred and thirty (130) students. These classes are selected on the basis of convenience because, the researcher himself is a mathematics teacher in these classes. This study was conducted over two weeks. A closed supervision was made by the researcher in the class to know the view of the students towards collaboration.

Among the four group (A, B, C, D) of each class VII and IX, researcher had selected only one particular group from each class. For the convenience, the group A of class VII consisting 31 students and group C of class IX consisting 28 students were selected. In this sense researcher seemed biased too.

The methodology of this study was quantitative methods supported by subjective judgment. In the completion of two weeks teaching using collaborative method of instruction a questionnaire survey was conducted with the students. This questionnaire survey enabled to get quantitative data. Also student's behaviors, narratives, gossiping in and outside the class were carefully recorded to further identify the attitude and behavior of students within their group setting in the classroom,

* Teacher, Buddhanilkanth School, Kathmandu

students' reflections during teaching, peer discussions and their personal reflection.

A set of questionnaire was developed which consists of both open and closed questions. Likert scale is used to study each closed item. The questionnaire contains four sections demographic, assessment of group involvement, attitudinal scale and open answer. Microsoft excel 2016 is used to aid data analysis of numerical data. The data collected from observation and field notes were also analyzed to support the quantitative findings.

It is thought all the participants had given their response sensibly. As it was explained to the students that teacher further selects pedagogy in accordance with their response. So, the response rate in this research was hundred percent. Hence, the rate of response for this research was quite appropriate and sufficient. The total number of participant in the study was fifty-nine. The number of boys are thirty-nine and that of girls is twenty.

Since this study is the researcher's try to his student only so it has small sample size. As sample size is small the study cannot be generalized further in other context. Furthermore, this study was conducted for a short period, two weeks only. Literature related to constructivism and collaborative learning were reviewed. They had given valuable insights related to constructivism and collaborative instruction for the study.

The first active step toward any inquiry is to identify the concern or issues and explain them in answerable form McLeish (2009). So this article is an attempt to identify the students' attitudes towards cooperative learning and its usefulness on classroom participation of students. This article will be helpful to formulate the pedagogic strategies in the mathematics classroom.

Constructivism and Collaborative Learning

Constructivism as a theory of education describes that, students' learning is basically shaped by what the learner already knows. So, constructivists teaching methods are student centered. They basically focus on the creation, exploration and development of new knowledge (Bhowmik, 2014). In relation to this Simon (1995) argued that, human beings have no access to an objective reality. Human beings are always driven by their instinct that they cannot simply give up but construct knowledge from their anthropomorphic view. These all perceptions and experiences are mediated through our previous knowledge.

In addition to this, Simon (1995) further explained, constructivism as a non-positivist philosophy. It accepts reality as a construct of human mind. Thus, reality is perceived to be subjective. In constructivist approach learners play an active role in 'constructing' their own meaning. Epistemologically, constructivism is the theory that knowledge is not something which we acquire but something that we produce; that the objects in an area of inquiry are not there to be discovered, but are invented or constructed (Mautner, 1996).

Upadhyay (2064 B.S.) interprets constructivism as a movement that extends beyond the belief of cognitivists. It considers the engagement of students in meaningful experiences as the essence of learning. Therefore, the role of instruction is not to dispense facts but to provide students with ways to construct the knowledge. Moreover, the ultimate measure of learning is based on the ability of the students to use knowledge to facilitate thinking in different life situations. So, it can be said that learners should create their own interpretation of the world of information and learning as

expansion of one's horizon of knowledge where learner constructs their meanings from their collective experiences. It can be said that constructivism is one of the most important theories that translates pupils' own understandings into classroom practices.

Constructivism stands on completely new ground, often in direct opposition to both behaviorism and maturationism. (Fosnot & Perry, 1996). Its goal is to focus on concept development and deep understandings rather than developing behaviors or skills. Similarly, collaborative learning is one of the classroom strategies based on constructivist ground. Belbase (2011) explained, mind is like a connected network of self and other. Mind is seen not only in individual context, but it is expanded to be a part of broader social context, and construction of meaning is considered as social phenomena.

Ernst von Glasersfeld a pioneer for radical constructivism explained the constructivism as theory of knowing. It oppose to the theory of knowledge (Glasersfeld, 1995). From this point of view, knowing is the idea of correspondence with reality is replaced by the idea of fit. Knowledge is good knowledge if it fits within the constraints of experiential reality and does not collide with them. This fit must be attained not only insofar as a cognitive structure, a scheme, a theory, have to remain viable in the face of new experience or experiments, but also in that they prove compatible with the other schemes and theories one is using. In mathematics, constructivism refers to the view that mathematical objects are admissible in a theory only if there is an effective method by which they can, ideally, be constructed. (Mautner, 1996).

Constructivist theories provide the basis for co-operative and collaborative learning.

Vidakovic and Martin explained that we internalize culture and externalize it by passing it on. By missing an opportunity for externalization, we limit internalization; that is to say, if we do not have the chance to explain our thought to someone else we fail to solidify learning (Gupta, 2008). In order to solidify the knowledge both process of internalization and externalization is required. For the effective internalization and externalization, group collaboration is very important.

Among different teaching strategies based on constructivism, collaborative learning is an important learning strategy for educators to use in their classrooms (Eady & Lockyer, 2013). It has been discussed and used by many teachers and educators in the domain of teaching and learning. Collaborative learning is a situation in which two or more students work together to search for understanding or meaning. Furthermore, Eady & Lockyer (2013) described that collaboration is also deep-rooted in Vygotsky's theory of learning.

Collaborative learning involves students to jointly set common goals, sharing responsibility of obtaining these goals and working together to achieve these goals using each other's expertise. According to Williams & Sheridan (2010), Collaborative learning, is a situation in which particular forms of interaction among people are expected to occur, which would trigger learning mechanisms, but there is no guarantee that the expected interactions will actually occur.

Study of Attitude

According to Hogg and Vaughan (2011), an attitude is a relatively enduring organization of beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards socially significant objects, groups, events or symbols. Citing Gordon Allport,

Hogg & Vaughan (2011) further explained:

...the concept of attitudes is probably the most distinctive and indispensable concept in contemporary American social psychology. No other term appears more frequently in the experimental and theoretical literature.

According to Crede & Kuncel (2008), attitudes is usually used to refer to a person's positive attitude toward the specific act and her/his acceptance and approval of that act. Thurstone and Chave (1929) explained attitude as the degree of positive or negative effect associated with some psychological object.

A study conducted by McLeish (2009) on the 'Attitude of Students Towards Cooperative Learning Methods at Knox Community College' claimed that, due to students fear, apprehension and past experiences many students prefer to work on their own rather than within a group. In a guide for teachers published by World Education Inc (2009), Cambodia, suggested that the children learn actively, learn to help one another, gets child to child learning support and an improved motivation can be obtained using cooperative learning methods. These two contrasting views motivated me to study the attitude of the students toward collaborative learning in our context.

Findings

The study has revealed that, among total (59) students, nine (9) students do not like to work in group and the remaining fifty (50) students like to work in group. The percentage of the students like to work in a group was 85% of the total participant. It showed that the attitude of the student is found to be positive towards working in a group.

As far as concerns related to the group size that most of the participants who like to work

in group preferred smaller group having less than 8 students. While dividing into groups they were found to be quite selective and they appeal for making smaller group with the friend closed with them.

The proportion of the students having low degree of preference of collaborative learning was quite less compared to students who showed high degree of preference. Furthermore, significant number of student remain neutral. Moreover, the number of students having high degree of preference was high toward collaborative learning. So, it can be said that, most of the students believe on collaborative learning for their academic progress. It means that students showed the moderately positive attitude towards collaborative learning.

Students have positive response that they can achieve more if they work together. Which comprises the 65% of the total population. 24% of the students remain neutral means they can achieve equally whether they are in group or alone. Whereas, only 12% of the students feel that they can achieve better when working alone which comprises the students of all kinds. Explaining the situation in terms of gender; girls were found to believe that they can work better in the group than in isolation as compared to the boys. The percentage of the boys who strongly believe that the working in group will yield better output is 21%, whereas that of the girls is 50%. From this analysis, the attitude of the girls found to be quite more positive towards collaborative learning than that of boys.

Moreover, the willingness of the student to participate in group activities was quite appraisable. About 66% of the students wanted to willingly participate in their group activities. Furthermore the girls (70%) are found to be participate more willingly than

boys (64%) of their respective group. Also, many students (70%) believed that the group learning helps them to socialize. There was very few (10%) students who believed that the group learning does not help them to socialize. There is no significant gender wise difference between the degrees of positive response to 'the group work helps students to socialize more'. Both girls and boys strongly believe (70% of each group) that group work helps them to socialize more.

It was found that very large number of students (70%) believe that the group activities assist them a lot in their learning. And very few (10%) students believe that the group activities do not help them to learn anything new. Also, the percentage of girls who believe that the group learning activities makes their learning easier is very high (85%) compared to the response received from the boys (61%). And there is not any girl who thinks that the group learning activities do not make their learning easier.

From the above analysis about the attitude towards collaborative learning it can be inferred that the general tendency of the student is positive towards collaborative learning. At the same time a significant number of students remains neutral. Furthermore, during closed observation and from open question the researcher has found that some students like collaborative learning in specific questions and chapters such as verbal questions and arithmetic. From the field notes and the close observation, the researcher found that the collaborative learning increases the students' participation in the classroom over the conventional learning. Students were found engaged and participated in most of the class activities every time the researcher introduces in the class.

Conclusion

Based on the findings the following conclusion can be derived:

1. Majority of the students have believed that they can do better in groups rather than working alone. But a significant number of students remained neutral. So, it is advisable to use collaborative learning in the benefit of majority of the students keeping in the mind to those who do not like collaborative instruction. So, collaborative learning will be useful to improve students learning achievement if the teacher makes a wise selection of the chapter or problem that can be taught using collaborative instruction.
2. The collaborative learning has very significant impact in classroom participation. Those students who did not participate more in classroom interactions before using collaborative instruction were likely to participate more in classroom interactions.
3. Because of the team spirit the students were highly motivated toward their studies.

Recommendations

The findings and the conclusion of the research suggest following recommendations.

1. It is advisable to use collaborative instruction because the students had shown positive attitudes towards it.
2. Not all the chapters and problems are suitable to teach using collaborative instruction so, the teacher must assess all the questions and the chapters for the suitability of the method.
3. It is advisable to curriculum planners and developers to integrate as much as activity based problem in the textbooks and the curricula.

4. While using collaborative instruction it is advisable that teacher should use competition as a tool for motivation
5. The group formed should be of uniform type so that there are equal number of members in each group.
6. A large-scale study using a more questions of other dimension should be done to generalize the result.

References

- Belbase, S. (2011). *Radical versus Social Constructivism: Dilemma, Dialogue, and Defense*. Retrieved from ERIC: Institute of Education Sciences: files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED525159.pdf
- Bhowmik, M. (2014). Constructivism approach in mathematics teaching and assessment of mathematical understanding. *Basic Research Journal of Education Research and Review*, 9-12.
- Crede, M., & Kuncel, N. R. (2008). Study Habits, Skills, and Attitudes. *Perspective on Psychological Science*, 425-453.
- Dingfelder, S. (2007, 04). *Schema-based instruction improves math skills*. Retrieved from American Psychological Association: <http://www.apa.org/monitor/apr07/schema.aspx>
- Eady, M. J., & Lockyer, L. (2013). Tools for learning: technology and teaching strategies. *Learning to Teach in the Primary School*, 71.
- Fosnot, C. T., & Perry, R. S. (1990). *Constructivism: Theory, Perspectives, and Practice*. (C. Twomey, Ed.) New York: Teacher College Press.
- Glaserfeld, E. v. (1995). *Radical Constructivism: A Way of Knowing and Learning*. *Studies in Mathematics Education Series: 6*. London: The Falmer Press.
- Gupta, A. (2008). Constructivism and Peer Collaboration in Elementary Mathematics Education: The Connection to Epistemology. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 381-386.
- Hogg, M. A., & Vaughan, G. M. (2011). *Social Psychology*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Mautner, T. (1996). *A Dictionary of Philosophy*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Limited.
- McLeish, K. (2009). *Attitude of Students Towards Cooperative Learning Methods at Knox Community*. Jamaica: Unpublished.
- Poudel, N. (2016). *Constructivism in Teaching: A Document Based Study*. Unpublished.
- Simon, M. A. (1995). Reconstructing Mathematics Pedagogy From a Constructivist Perspectives. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 114-145.
- Thurstone, L. L., & Chave, E. E. (1929). *Measurement of Attitude*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Upadhyay, H. P. (2064 B.S.). *New Trends in Mathematics Instruction*. Kathmandu: Vidyarthi Prakashan(P) Ltd.
- Williams, P., & Sheridan, S. (2010). Conditions for Collaborative Learning and Constructive Competition In School. *Educational Research*, 335-350.
- World Education Inc. (2009). *Cooperative Learning Theory & Practice*. Cambodia: World Education-Cambodia.